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Stage II Annealing of Chemical Radiation Damage in Strontium Nitrate

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THE isothermal annealing of chemical radiation damage in various ionic nitrates has been investigated and it has been observed that the recovery takes place as a continuous process¹⁻⁵. In some preliminary investigations on isochronal annealing and annealing in linear tempering of chemical radiation damage in γ -irradiated strontium nitrate in this laboratory it has been observed that the recombination takes place in two stages, one between 180-260° and the other above 260°. The details of the

kinetics of the recovery process in the temperature range 180-260° have already been reported⁶. This communication reports the kinetics of the thermal annealing process taking place in the second stage (270-300°).

Experimental

The same sample of irradiated strontium nitrate employed in the previous investigations⁶ was used. Isothermal runs were made in the temperature range 270-300° as before. The analytical procedure followed was also the same as that reported earlier⁶.

Results and Discussion

Data on the kinetics of annealing are presented in Fig. 1. The φ -t characteristic is the same as that obtained in the lower temperature range. The magnitude of annealing in the higher temperature range is greater as expected.

The annealing data obtained have been analysed on the basis of models developed by Fletcher and Brown^{6,7} and by Waite^{8,9} for interstitial vacancy recombination and also on the basis of conventional chemical kinetics¹⁰. The application of Fletcher-Brown treatment^{6,7} shows that the annealing data fit the following combination of a first order and second order process

$$\varphi = 0.14[1 - \exp(-t'/1.031)] + 0.86[1/1 + 297.6/t']$$

where φ is the fraction annealed and t' the equivalent time of annealing⁶ at 280°. The activation

Fig. 1. Annealing of γ -irradiation damage in strontium nitrate.

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Fig. 2. Energetics of various kinetic processes.

energy of the process is 23.1 kcal mole⁻¹ (Fig. 2). The corresponding energy in the first stage of annealing is 18.3 kcal.

The activation energy of the stage II annealing process calculated from the temperature dependence of $\varphi/t^{1/2}$ as required by the Waite theory^{8,9} is 24.7 kcal mole⁻¹ (Fig. 2). The activation energy of the stage I process⁵ is 18.5 kcal. It is of interest to note that in each stage both the Fletcher-Brown and the Waite treatments give values of the energy of activation which are very nearly the same.

Analysis of data by conventional chemical kinetics¹⁰ reveals that the mean values of the proportions of the original nitrite that recombines by the first and second order mechanisms are 14 and 86 per cent instead of 8 and 92 per cent in the first stage. These values are also independent of temperature. The activation energies of the first and second order processes are 9.3 and 25.3 kcal respectively. In the lower temperature range the corresponding values are 8.9 and 15.0 kcal respectively.

It is evident from the results that annealing of chemical radiation damage in γ -irradiated strontium nitrate is not a continuous process and that it takes place in two stages. The damage species that escape recombination at the lower temperatures recombine at higher temperatures as is evident from the increase in the value of the energy of activation of

the recovery process. Similar results have been observed in the case of annealing of neutron irradiation damage in potassium bromate¹¹.

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Membrane Reflection Coefficient

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IN a recent communication¹ dealing with the membrane selectivity and reflection coefficient, σ , earlier defined by Stavermann², it has been shown by Singh *et al*¹ that the idea advanced by Shrivastava *et al*³, refuting the justifiability of the criterion for the description of the selectivity of ideally semipermeable membranes even when interaction between the permeating solute and solvent is considered, has no validity. They have also examined, separately, the permeation of an electrolyte mixture solution containing solutes 1 and 2, wherein interaction between various constituents of the solution is either (a) completely ignored or (b) considered, in the light of non-equilibrium thermodynamics⁴. In their analysis¹ they have concluded⁵ that when permeation of solute, is completely checked σ_1 and σ_2 are unity only when

$$\Delta C_1 = \Delta C_2 = \Delta C/2 \quad \dots (1)$$

where the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to the solutes 1 and 2 respectively. The analysis, probably, has been applied to the case of dilute solutions where the laws of osmotic pressure hold good.

The above conclusion arrived at by the authors¹ appears to be misleading which would be apparent from what has been discussed below.

Equation (10) (Ref. 1), by substitution of the results from equation (11) (Ref. 1), presents only a specific case when the components 1 and 2 are equal in concentrations, each being equal to $\Delta C/2$, as has been observed by the authors⁵. The above observation, read with equation (11) (Ref. 1) also compels us to recognise $\Delta\pi_1 = \Delta\pi_2 = \Delta\pi/2$ (which obviously follows when we equate $\Delta C_1 = \Delta C_2 = \frac{1}{2}\Delta C$) and in that event the discussion of the authors¹ converges to the discussion of only a very selected and simple case of a solution having solutes of equal concentration. It is only due to this fallacy or the use of this specific rider that a factor $(\Delta C/2\Delta C_1)$ appears in the second term of the

second parentheses of equation(10). Similarly $(\Delta C/2\Delta C_2)$ appears in the second term of the third parentheses of the same equation. Presumption of such a situation deprives this finding of the authors¹ of assuming the general character. The discrepancy in equation (10) (Ref. 1) may, however, be circumvented by modifying the approach as discussed below :

$$\Delta\pi_1 = RT\Delta C_1$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\Delta\pi}{\Delta C} = \frac{\Delta\pi_1}{\Delta C_1} = \frac{\Delta\pi_2}{\Delta C_2} = \frac{\Delta\pi_1 + \Delta\pi_2}{\Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2} \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{or } \frac{\Delta\pi}{\Delta C} = \frac{\Delta\pi_1 + \Delta\pi_2}{\Delta C}$$

$$\text{or } \Delta\pi = \Delta\pi_1 + \Delta\pi_2 \quad \dots (3)$$

($\Delta C = \Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2$ will be applicable to the system under consideration¹). It may be noted that ΔC_1 and ΔC_2 may be equal, but not necessarily ; it may be different as well. In fact ΔC_1 may assume any value irrespective of the value of ΔC_2 without affecting the dilute nature of the solution. This, certainly, is a more generalized approach. In each case the condition $\Delta C = \Delta C_1 + \Delta C_2$ will hold so long as the dilute nature of the solution is retained. Thus it would be clear that our equation (3) is not equivalent to equation (2) of K.S. - R.S. (Ref. 1) which makes use of a specific rider discussed above.

Coming to the last portion of the paper¹, after equation (17) (Ref. 1), dealing with the situation where interaction between the solvent and the solutes has been taken into consideration, J_v has been shown to be given by equation (18) (Ref. 1). Equation (2) will still be valid under the situation of the system discussed in the paper¹. Under the circumstances, we find that with the modification as suggested in equation (2) the forms of equations (19-20) (Ref. 1), obtained from equation (18) (Ref. 1), remain unaltered while those of equations (21-23) (Ref. 1) undergo a little change. In equation (21) (Ref. 1) the term $\Delta C/2\Delta C_1$, outside the parentheses of the second part of the second term (associated with $\Delta\pi_1^*$) of the r.h.s. will vanish. Similarly the term $\Delta C/2\Delta C_2$ outside the parentheses of the third portion of the second term (associated with $\Delta\pi_2^{**}$) of the r.h.s. will also vanish. As regards equations (22-23) (Ref. 1) σ_1 and σ_2 will assume the

following forms ^{***} respectively. For smooth read-

* Which has been erroneously printed as $\Delta\pi$.

** Erroneously printed as $\Delta\pi^2$.

*** The printing mistakes and the omissions in the original equations have been taken into consideration in writing our present equations.

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